

REVIEW ARTICLE

**A STUDY ON DENTAL CARIES PREVALENT AMONG
SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN IN SELECTED AREAS IN PUDUCHERRY**

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Abstract:

The overall health well-being education and overall development can be affected by oral health prevalent in school going children. The lack of availability and affordability of oral health services not only results in aggravation of the diseases but also enhances the cost of treatment and care. Objectives of The Study: (i) To gather general information from the school going children aged 5-16 years. (ii) To evaluate the oral health status from the school going children aged 5-16 years. (iii) to create awareness regarding oral health and educate them on the prevention of dental caries. The present study comprised of school going children from urban areas of Union Territory of Puducherry. The Sample size was limited to 30, due to time limits, and were between the age group of 5 -16 years including Pre-School, Middle School and Higher Secondary School going children. The Collection of raw data was done by personal interview and Questionnaire method. In case of Pre-school children, their information was gathered from their respective parents. The general information of the children, their dental status, and type of food consumed were collected.

Keywords: Oral Health, Dental Caries, Diet.

1. Introduction:

Oral Health is an integral component of general health. It has also become clear that causative and risk factors in oral diseases are often the same as those implicated in the major general diseases (WHO,2003). The lack of availability and affordability of oral health services not only results in aggravation of the diseases but also enhances the cost of treatment and care.

1.1 Objectives of the Study:

- i. To gather general information from the school going children aged 5-16 years.
- ii. To evaluate the oral health status from the school going children aged 5-16 years.
- iii. to create awareness regarding oral health and educate them on the prevention of dental caries.

2. Review of Literature:

Dental Caries also known as tooth decay or a cavity, is a disease where bacterial processes change carbohydrate like sugar in food left on teeth to acid that demineralises hard tooth structure. A person experiencing caries may not be aware of the disease. The earliest sign of a new carious lesion is the appearance of a chalky white spot on the surface of tooth, indicating an area of demineralisation of the enamel. This is referred to as incipient decay. As the lesion continues to demineralize, it can turn brown but will eventually into a cavity. Before the cavity forms, the process is reversible, but once a cavity forms, the lost tooth cannot be regenerated. A lesion which appears brown and shiny suggests dental caries were once present but the demineralization process has stopped, leaving a stain, brown spot which is dull in appearance is probably a sign of active caries (Neville, B.W, Damm. D,2002).

There are four main causes which lead to caries formation:

- (i) a tooth surface -Dental caries can occur on any surface of a tooth which is exposed to the oral cavity, but not the structures which are retained within the bone. Though most trapped food is left between teeth, over 80 percent of cavities occur inside pits and fissures on chewing surfaces where brushing, fluoride and saliva cannot reach to demineralise tooth like on easy to reach surfaces that develop few cavities.
- (ii) Caries- causing Bacteria- the mouth contains a wide variety of oral bacteria, but only a few species of bacteria like *Streptococcus mutans*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Actinomyces viscosus*, *Nocardia species.*, and *Streptococcus mutans* are closely associated with caries, particularly root caries.
- (iii) Fermentable carbohydrates- Bacteria in a person's mouth convert glucose, fructose, and most commonly sucrose (table sugar) into acids such as Lactic acid through a glycolytic process called fermentation. If left in contact with the tooth, these acids may cause demineralisation, which is the dissolution of its mineral content. If demineralisation continues over time, enough mineral content may be lost so that the soft organic material left behind disintegrates, forming a cavity or a hole (Banting. D.W, 2006).
- (iv) Time- After meals or snacks, the bacteria in the mouth metabolise sugar, resulting in an acidic by-product which decreases pH. As time progresses, the pH returns to normal due to the buffering capacity of saliva and the dissolved mineral content of tooth surfaces. Since teeth are vulnerable during these acidic periods, the development of dental caries relies heavily on the frequency of acid exposure (Banting. D.W, 2006).

3. Methodology:

3.1 Selection of Area:

As the study deals with dental caries prevalent mostly among school going children the investigator felt the immediate need to elucidate from this age group only.

3.2 Selection of Sample:

The present study comprised of school going children from urban areas as the investigator had easy access to approach the subject and hence areas situated in the Union Territory of Puducherry comprised of Nellithope, Muthialpet, Saram, and New Bus Stand Areas.

3.3 Derivation of Sample Size:

The Sample size was limited to 30, due to time limits, and were between the age group of 5 -16 years including Pre-School, Middle School and Higher Secondary School going children.

3.4 Selection of Tools and Techniques:

The Collection of raw data was done by personal interview and Questionnaire method. In case of Pre-school children, their information was gathered from their respective parents. The general information of the children, their dental status, and type of food consumed were collected.

3.5 Consolidation and Analysis of Data:

The collected data was carefully tabulated, analysed and interpreted under result and discussion.

4. Result and Discussion:

4.1 Age of the Respondents:

Table 1: Age of The Respondents

Age (Years)	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
5-10	5	17
11-16	25	83

From the above table, it was found among the school children that nearly 17 percent of the children were between 5-10 years, 83 percent were between 11-16 years.

4.2 Sex of the Respondents:

Table 2: Sex of The Respondents

Sex	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Male	10	33
Female	20	67

It is clear from the above table that among the 10 sample, 10 of them were boys and 20 were girls.

4.3 Education of the Respondents:

Table 3: Education of The Respondents

Education	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Primary	8	27
High School	6	20
Higher Secondary	16	53

The above table shows that 27 percent were in primary education, 20 percent were in middle school, 20 percent in High School and 53 percent in Higher Secondary School.

4.4 Body Mass Index (BMI) of the Respondents:

Table 4: Body Mass Index (BMI) of The Respondents

Body Mass Index (BMI)	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Normal	15	50
Underweight	07	23
Overweight	08	27

4.5 Brand of Tooth Paste Used by the Respondents:

Table 5: Body Mass Index (BMI) of The Respondents

Brand of Tooth Paste	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Colgate	19	64
Dabour	04	13
Close-Up	01	03
Pepsodent	02	07
Oral-B	04	13

Among the 30 respondents 64 percent of the respondents used Colgate Paste, 13 percent Dabour Ayurvedic paste, 3 percent utilised Close-Up paste, 7 percent of the respondents used Pepsodent Tooth paste, 13 percent of the respondents used Oral-B paste.

4.6 Type of Bristles Used by the Respondents:

Table 6: Type of Bristles Used by the Respondents

Type of Bristles	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Hard Bristle	11	37
Soft Bristle	19	63

37 percent of the respondents used tooth brush with hard bristles and 63 percent with soft bristles.

4.7 usage of Tooth Powder by the Respondents:

Table 7: Usage of Tooth Powder by the Respondents

Usage of Tooth Powder	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Yes	02	07
No	28	93

From the above table it is clear that 07 percent were using tooth powder such as Dabur, Gopal tooth powder and the remaining 93 percent used tooth paste.

4.8 Number of Times Brushing the Teeth:

Table 8: Number of Times Brushing the Teeth by the Respondents

No. of Times Brushing the Teeth	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Less than once per day	06	20
Once per day	17	57
Twice per Day	07	23
More than Twice a Day	-	-

Out of 30 children, 20 percent of them brushed less than once a day, 57 percent once a day, 23 percent brushed twice per day and none were found to brush more than twice per day.

4.9 Duration of Brushing the Teeth:

Table 9: Duration of Brushing The Teeth By The Respondents

Duration of Brushing the Teeth	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
< 1 Minute	03	10
1 Minute	13	43
2 Minutes	14	47
>2 Minutes	-	-

The above table depicts that 10 percent brushed less than one minute, 43 percent of the respondent's brushed for one minute, and 47 percent brushed for two minutes and none were found to brush more than two minutes, in case of pre-school who were assisted by their parents, or siblings, care-takers.

4.10 Time of Brushing the Teeth:

Table 10: Time of Brushing the Teeth by the Respondent

Brushing Time	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Morning		93
Afternoon	-	-
Before going To Bed	02	07
Other Time	-	-

Above Table, clearly shows that among the 30 children, 93 percent brushed regularly in the morning, and 7 percent of the respondents brushed before retiring to bed.

4.11 Cleansing Agents Used for Brushing the Teeth:

Table 11: Cleansing Agents Used for Brushing the Teeth by the Respondent

Cleansing Agents Used	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Tooth Paste	30	100
Dental Floss	-	-
Mouth Wash	-	-
Tooth Pick for Floss	-	-

From the above table, clearly shows that among the 30 respondents, 100 percent of them used tooth paste only and did not use any other cleansing agent.

4.12 Number of Respondents Affected by Dental Plaque

Table 12: Number of Respondents Affected by Dental Plaque

Dental Plaque	No. of Subjects (N=30)	Percent
Soft dentin	06	20
Staining of Teeth	05	17
Hard Dentin	-	-
I don't Know	19	63

The above table shows that 20 percent of the respondents, used soft dentins, 17 percent had stained teeth, 63 percent were unaware of it.

4.13 Symptoms of Dental Plaques Noticed in the Respondents

Figure 1: Symptoms of dental plaques noticed in the respondents

The above graph depicts that 3 percent had inflammation of Teeth, 30 percent had discolouration of Teeth, 43 percent suffered from dental caries, whereas 24 percent didn't have any knowledge about it.

4.14 Frequent Consumption of Confectionary or Baked Food Items by the Respondents

Figure 2: Frequent consumption of confectionary or baked food items by the respondents

Majority (73 percent) of them reported to have chewing gums, sweets, candies, chocolates, cakes, pastries and going to bed without rinsing their mouth after consumption.

Nutrition Education was given by the investigator using Power Point Presentation and in the form of Charts regarding Dental hygiene, foods to be included and excluded to prevent Dental Caries which comprised of 30 minutes, good response was received both from the parents and their children.

Conclusion:

Thus, to conclude dental caries can be prevented by visiting the dentist to remove plaques and maintaining proper dental hygiene and taking fewer sticky foods and rinsing the teeth after consumption of food.

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